

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

INVESTIGATION OF OIL WELLS UNDER STEADY-STATE FILTRATION CONDITIONS AT THE ZHETYBAI FIELD

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Abstract

This article discusses the study of oil wells under steady-state filtration conditions at the Zhetybai field. Recently, a number of multi-deposit oil and gas deposits have been opened on the territory of Western Kazakhstan. However, at the same time, numerous deposits with small and medium flow rates continue to operate. Therefore, the design and implementation of new, more advanced methods for the development and production of oil and gas wells remains an urgent problem. Here, a large field of activity is still open to process engineers and designers.

Keywords: research, well, steady-state filtration modes, formation, flow rate, oilfield.

Research. The study of oil wells under steady-state filtration conditions is an important stage for determining the main parameters of the borehole formation and optimizing the oil production process. During the steady-state filtration regime, wells are in a stable state when the distribution of pressure and oil inflow into the reservoir undergoes minimal changes.

Various methods are used to study oil wells under steady-state filtration conditions, including:

Rate Transient Analysis (RTA): This method is based on the analysis of changes in oil flow over time. According to the flow rate and time data, it is possible to determine the characteristics of the formation, such as permeability and volume of oil in the formation.

Material balance: The material balance method is based on the analysis of changes in the volume of oil in the reservoir and on the surface, taking into account natural and artificial influences. Based on the results of the analysis, it is possible to determine the oil reserves in the reservoir and the oil recovery coefficient.

Pressure Transient Analysis, (PTA): With PTA, changes in bottom-hole pressure are investigated during the steady-state filtration regime. According to the data of downhole pressure and its changes, it is possible to determine the characteristics of the formation and well parameters, such as permeability and skin factor [1-2].

Interference testing: This method is based on the analysis of the influence of one well on another in a steady filtration mode. Based on the results of the analysis, it is possible to determine the characteristics of the formations and the connections between the wells.

During the analyzed period, 187 hydrodynamic studies (GDI) were performed in 160 wells at the Zhetybai field, which is 21.3% of the current fund of the field. Of these, 32 studies (5.7% of the fund) were carried out by the level restoration method (KVU), 37 studies (6.6%) by the pressure restoration method in

injection wells with efficiency registration and 91 studies (16.2%) by the method of steady-state sampling (MUO). The noted hydrodynamic studies were performed by the Holding Scientific and Technical Center Geoservice by the service company ALSTRON LLP with subsequent data processing and interpretation of the results using a specialized software product PanSystem. Measurements of changes in the dynamic level and annular pressure were performed by the Sudos-automatic device, Sudos-automatic 2 and PPS-25. The largest number of GDI was performed on the horizon Yu-8 (24% of the current horizon fund), the smallest (1 issl.) on the Yu-4, Yu-7 and Yu-13 horizons.

Based on the results of graphoanalytic processing of the curves, the following parameters were determined: flow model, permeability, skin factor, reservoir pressure, piezo conductivity and hydraulic conductivity of the formation.

The duration of registration of level recovery curves in producing wells ranged from 1.2 days (Yu-9 sq. 1207) to 19.5 days (Yu- 11 sq. 483), the duration of registration of pressure drop curves in injection wells varies from 2.5 days (Yu-9 sq. No. 1174) to 15.8 days (Yu-10 No. 259), the average duration of the MUO study is 6.5 days when the well is operating in 4 stationary modes (levels).

Studies using the steady-state level (MUI) method have not been performed at this stage [1-4].

The results of research on operational facilities in the post-project period, including the intervals for changing parameters along the horizons, are presented in Table 1.

According to the results of GDI modeling, the most typical model for these conditions is a radial homogeneous reservoir model with a radial flow pattern of liquid to the bottom of the well. The second type of reservoir model is a vertical crack (while maintaining uniformity of flow and limited

conductivity), the crack surface skin varies according to studies from -5.83 to 6.44, the fluid flow in the formation is linear and radial. The presence of a crack in the borehole zone of wells is the result of previous hydraulic fracturing work carried out here, which turned out to be quite effective.

The results of the comprehensive hydrodynamic studies of wells of the Zhetybai field in 2018 made it possible to assess the condition of the bottom-hole zone of production wells, determine the filtration properties of the horizons being developed in specific zones, select the most optimal operating mode of the studied wells, analyze the current state of development and select wells for production intensification. A significant part of the hydrodynamic studies in 2018 were performed in wells Yu- 5ab, Yu-8, Yu-9 and Yu-10 facilities. The most improved productive and filtration parameters of the formations are fixed at the Yu-2+3 and Yu-10 facilities, so the oil productivity per 1 m of effective reservoir thickness is on average 1.5 m³/day/MPa/m, varying from 0.009 to 12.8 m³/day/MPa/m wells. The hydroconductivity is 0.056 mm²•m/(MPa•s), the range of change is 0.00051 mm²•m/(MPa•s) – 0.364 mm²•m/(MPa•s), the average permeability is 6.21•10⁻³ mm² (0.06•10⁻³ mm²)

For the period from 2018 to the first half of 2019, the Alstron service company performed hydrodynamic studies at the field: in well No. 23 - KVU and in well No. 5 - IK.

Data processing and determination of filtration and capacitance properties, as well as the flow regime, was carried out using a specialized software product PanSystem with the construction of graphs in logarithmic coordinates and modeling of the research process. Based on the results of graphoanalytic processing of the curves, the following parameters were determined: flow model, permeability, skin factor, Rpl, piezo conductivity and hydraulic conductivity of the formation [2-5].

The graphs (Figure 1) show the pressure change curve, its derivative, plotted in semi-logarithmic coordinates. The flow model and filtration-capacitance properties of the reservoir are determined by the derivative.

According to the data of the well study, an indicator diagram is constructed in the flow-depression coordinates in several modes, and in the case of a rectilinear indicator diagram, the productivity coefficient is determined. The figure below shows a graph of the constructed indicator curve (Figure 2).

Table 1 shows the results of the KVU processing for the analyzed period.

As can be seen from the table, the productivity coefficient for wells varies from 0.015 to 0.725 m³/day/MPa, the skin factor in both wells is negative, which characterizes the favorable state of the CCD.

Table 1

GDIS results

№ скв	Вид исследования	Дата замера	Проницаемость, мД	Пьезопроводность, м ² /с	Гидропроводность, м ³ */МПа*с	Коэффициент продуктивности, (м ³ /сут)/(кг/см ²)	Скин-фактор	Рпл., МПа	Рзаб., МПа
23	КВУ	16.06-12.09.2018	0,2	7,17	9,93	0,015	-4,3	36,3	16,8
5	ИК	22.08-31.08.2018	0,59	23,8	1,3	0,725	-1,9	30,7	27,7

In order to identify the extractive capabilities of productive deposits in wells, hydrodynamic studies using the method of steady-state sampling were carried out. Based on the results of these studies, indicator

diagrams are constructed, shown in Figures 1-2, which have a linear dependence of the flow rate on the depression on the reservoir or the flow rate on the average dynamic level.

Figure 1 – Well 23. Graph in semi-logarithmic coordinates

Figure 2 - Distribution of initial reservoir pressure by depth

In order to cause inflow in the wells, the previously perforated intervals were shot. The inflow was called in all wells by reducing downhole pressure, swabbing. Also, during the rehabilitation of exploration and production wells, hydrodynamic studies (GDI) were conducted to determine the parameters of deposits and reservoir pressures. The GDI was carried out by the level recovery method (MLD), followed by recalculation and construction of the pressure recovery curve (CVD).

In 2012-2017, the formation was tested on drill pipes (IPT) and 21 hydrodynamic studies were carried out using the pressure recovery method.

Investigation of oil wells under steady-state filtration conditions. Hydrodynamic methods.

Hydrodynamic methods, these include:

- non-stationary flooding;
- forced liquid extraction;
- involvement in the development of non-drained reserves;
- barrier and focal flooding.

The first group includes methods that are carried out through changing the operating modes of wells and, as a result, through changing the operating modes of the reservoir.

These methods are combined by the general concept of "non-stationary flooding" and include:

- cyclic flooding;
- changing the direction of filtration flows.

They are relatively easy to implement, do not require large economic costs and have been widely developed.

The methods are based on periodic changes in the mode of operation of the deposit by stopping and resuming water injection and extraction, due to which capillary and hydrodynamic forces are more fully used.

This contributes to the introduction of water into the formation zones that were not previously affected.

It should be started gradually, increasing the flow rate of individual wells by 30-50%, and then by 2-4 times.

The maximum value of the increase in selection is regulated by the capabilities of the well operation method used.

High-flow pumps or the use of a gas lift are required to carry out forced selection.

The operation of gas and oil fields is complicated by possible gas breakthroughs to the faces of producing wells, which significantly complicates their operation due to the high gas factor.

The essence of barrier flooding is that injection wells are located in the zone of gas-oil contact.

Water injection and extraction of gas and oil are regulated in such a way as to exclude mutual flows of oil into the gas part of the deposit, and gas into the oil part.

Focal flooding is an addition to the already implemented system of contour flooding or intra-contour flooding.

At the same time, groups of injection wells are located in areas of the formation that lag behind in terms of the intensity of use of oil reserves.

The scheme of the deposit $\Gamma_B < \frac{\sigma_H}{\pi}$ there is an inner copulation

$$\omega_H = \frac{\mu_B \ln \frac{\Gamma_B}{\Gamma_C}}{\pi n_n k \kappa_B h} + \frac{\mu_H \ln \frac{\sigma_H}{\pi \Gamma_B}}{\pi n_n k \kappa_H h} = \frac{1,08 \ln \frac{0,8}{0,75}}{3,14 \cdot 10 \cdot 0,135 \cdot 0,3 \cdot 43,2} + \frac{1,5 \ln \frac{0,8}{3,14 \cdot 0,8}}{3,14 \cdot 10 \cdot 0,135 \cdot 0,2 \cdot 43,2} = 0,9$$

we find the external resistance

$$\Omega_{H1} = \frac{\mu_B \ln \frac{R}{R_2}}{2\pi k h} = \frac{1,08 \ln \frac{1500}{900}}{2 \cdot 3,14 \cdot 0,135 \cdot 43,2} = \frac{0,510}{36,62} = 0,0139$$

R_1 and R_2 find the external resistance

$$\Omega_{H2} = \frac{\mu_b \ln \frac{R}{R_1}}{2\pi k h_{KB}} + \frac{\mu_b \ln \frac{R}{R_2}}{2\pi k h_{KH}} = \frac{1,08 \ln \frac{1500}{450}}{2 * 3,14 * 0,135 * 43,2 * 0,3} + \frac{1,5 \ln \frac{1500}{900}}{2 * 3,14 * 0,135 * 43,2 * 0,2} = \frac{1,2}{7,33} + \frac{0,766}{7,32} = \mathbf{0,163 + 0,1046} = \mathbf{0,267}$$

we find the ratio of time t and the initial balance R_b in

$$q * t = \pi (R_2 - R_1^2) * h * m * (1 - S_{CB} - S_{H_{OCT}}) = 3,14 * (900^2 - 450^2) * 43,2 * 17,2 * (1 - 0,2 - 0,1) = 992170166 = 992 * 10^6$$

Conclusion. Modern hydrodynamic research methods make it possible to obtain the most important parameters from field data, on the basis of which field development systems are designed, the oil production process is regulated and the effectiveness of the development of facilities is analyzed.

The filtration parameters of the deposit were determined using a simplified method. The hydraulic conductivity of the formation is $0.187 \text{ (mm}^2 \cdot \text{m)MPa} \cdot \text{s}$, permeability 0.4 mm^2 . The results of the theoretical calculation almost coincide with the results of the field data.

Adding values $R = 1.5 \text{ km}$, $h = 43.2 \text{ m}$, $R_1 = 450 \text{ m}$, $R_2 = 900 \text{ m}$, $r_c = 0.01 \text{ m}$, $n_1 = 5$, $n_2 = 10$, $n_n = 10$, $k = 0.135 \text{ mm}^2$, $m = 17.2\%$, $\mu_b = 1.08 \text{ MPa} \cdot \text{s}$, $\mu_h = 1.5 \text{ MPa} \cdot \text{s}$, $r_n = 874 \text{ [kg/m}^3, k_v = 0.3, k_n = 0.2$ calculated the ratio of time t and the initial balance R_b , it is $992 * 10^6$

The study of wells by the method of steady-state regimes and pressure reduction is recommended to be carried out in conjunction with the MUO study in order to obtain the full amount of information used in the interpretation.

Given the low reservoir and filtration properties of reservoir rocks of the deposit, it is necessary to conduct a complex of field studies to determine the optimal operating modes of producing wells with modes at and

below saturation pressure. The skin factor is usually chosen as the optimality parameter.

When the downhole pressure in the producing well decreases below the saturation pressure, it is necessary to optimize the operation of the well at the Zhetybai field by increasing the reservoir pressure.

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